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**Machine Learning and Computer
Vision for Detecting Radiata Pine
Tree Branch Locations for
Drone-based Prunings**

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Submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for
Doctor of Philosophy.

Abstract

This research investigates the developments and applications of machine learning and computer vision approaches to accurately detect radiata pine branches for drone-based pruning. Driven by the need to improve automation and efficiency in agriculture and forestry, this research addresses the challenge of accurately detecting the tree branches and measuring the distance from the camera position to tree branches to facilitate precise pruning. A primary objective is to develop a robust model that enables drones to accurately identify branch locations and compute their distances from the drone. This will be achieved through the integration of advanced computer vision techniques and machine learning algorithms. The expected outcomes of this research include improved accuracy and efficiency of drone-operated pruning systems, demonstrating the significant potential of deep learning technologies to advance automation in agriculture and forestry sectors.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Problem Statement

Pinus radiata, commonly known as radiata pine, is a highly valuable species extensively cultivated in New Zealand due to its rapid growth and versatile applications in forestry and timber industries. This species is essential for producing high-quality timber used in construction, paper manufacturing, and other wood-based products, significantly contributing to the economy [81][55]. For instance, in New South Wales, Australia, the radiata pine industry contributed approximately \$3 billion to the economy in 2021-22, highlighting its economic importance¹. However, to ensure the trees grow with strong, straight trunks and produce clear wood, which doesn't have knots, regular pruning is necessary. Traditionally performed manually, tree pruning and trimming are hazardous occupations globally, posing significant challenges and dangers. According to Tree Care Industry Magazine², in the United States alone, the Bureau of Labor Statistics reports a fatality rate of 110 per 100,000 tree trimmers and pruners, which is about 30 times higher than the average across all industries. Moreover, non-fatal injury rates for tree workers are also substantially higher, at approximately 239 injuries per 10,000 workers, compared to 89 per 10,000 across all industries. It is also challenging to find people who want to do the work because it is hard and dangerous.

The application of drones has significantly expanded due to technological advancements, yet their use in forestry, particularly for branch pruning, remains limited. Existing drone systems designed for pruning often require manual operation and can only cut thicker branches, relying on costly auxiliary equipment like LiDAR sensors, which hinders their widespread adoption [58]. To address these challenges, we aim to develop a drone equipped tool with a stereo camera and a pruning tool, capable of automatically detecting and pruning branches as thin as 10 mm. This system utilizes the stereo camera for branch identification and distance measurement, enabling autonomous pruning. By streamlining the design and enhancing sensor technology, this approach aims to make drone-based pruning more accessible and cost-effective, improving precision and efficiency in forestry management. This advancement in autonomous drone operations offers a versatile and economical solution for various applications beyond forestry, eliminating the need for extensive manual control or expensive auxiliary equipment.

To ensure this research proposal is comprehensive and self-contained, it is imperative to include detailed information on all relevant aspects, particularly the structural components of the drones utilized in this study. For an in-depth overview of these components,

¹<https://www.dpi.nsw.gov.au/dpi/climate/climate-vulnerability-assessment/forestry/radiata-pine>

²<https://tcimag.tcia.org/safety/tree-work-safety-by-the-numbers/>

please consult the following resource: <https://ucvision.org.nz/drones/>. This link provides critical insights into the design and specifications of the drones, with their testing process depicted in Figure 1.1.

The big research project is a collaborative effort involving multiple institutions, each contributing specific expertise. While other institutions focus on the physical construction of the drones, our research is concentrated on developing the vision detection and measurement algorithms for the cameras mounted on these drones. These algorithms are pivotal for accurately detecting branches and determining their precise positions in three-dimensional space, which is essential for guiding the drone's robotic knife to prune branches effectively. The primary objective of our research is to enhance the accuracy and reliability of branch detection, thereby improving the overall efficiency and safety of the autonomous pruning process.

Figure 1.1: The drone, equipped with a ZED mini camera for stereo vision and a robotic knife autonomously detects and prunes branches of radiata pine. The ZED mini camera enables the drone to accurately identify the branches, while the robotic knife precisely prunes them.

1.2 Motivations

To facilitate the accurate detection of the spatial position of tree branches by the drone's camera, this study incorporates both segmentation and depth evaluation techniques. The segmentation process effectively isolates the branches from the surrounding environment, while depth evaluation assesses their distance and orientation relative to the drone. The integration of these methodologies enables precise localization of the branches in three-dimensional space with respect to the camera, as demonstrated in Figure 1.2.

1.2.1 Research Significance

The aim of this research is to develop an advanced tree pruning technique using drone-based visual detection, which will significantly benefit New Zealand's agricultural science and technology sector with broad social and economic impacts. This technology mitigates the risk of injury and death associated with traditional manual pruning methods that necessitate

Figure 1.2: Our research motivation is structured into three key steps. First, branch segmentation is performed to isolate branches from the background using image processing techniques. Second, depth estimation is conducted to evaluate the distance and depth of these segmented branches. Third, by integrating the results of segmentation and depth assessment, the spatial position of the branches relative to the drone is determined, facilitating precise pruning.

workers to climb trees and identify branches, thereby enhancing worker safety. Automation of this process is essential for New Zealand, a country heavily reliant on agriculture and livestock, to maintain its competitive edge and improve operational efficiency[5][20][33].

We hope that the drone we develop will significantly improve pruning efficiency, reduce labor intensity and associated costs, and optimize agricultural processes[60]. In later stages, human workers will monitor the process rather than work on the front lines, attracting more researchers to the industry and stabilizing production. This promotes sustainable agriculture, reduces environmental impact, and provides a more eco-friendly solution for future production. Currently applied to *Pinus radiata*, this technology be extended to other tree species in the future. These advancements positively impact New Zealand’s agricultural production and economy by increasing productivity, boosting the rural economy, enhancing sector resilience, and creating jobs[85].

1.2.2 Current Limitations

The primary limitations of this study involve the absence of an existing benchmark dataset for detecting tree branches requiring pruning, particularly for Radiata Pine, which complicates the development and validation of detection models. Additionally, the challenge of detecting small objects, such as thin branches, compared to larger ones is more difficulty since more prominent objects adds to the complexity of accurate identification. Accurate distance measurement between the drone and the branches using the Stereolabs ZED Mini binocular camera³ is necessary for effective pruning but can be difficult to achieve. Finally, refining the detection models to enhance accuracy and reduce processing time is crucial for achieving reliable, real-time solutions.

The absence of an existing dataset poses a significant challenge in research on camera-based detection of tree branches needing pruning, especially for Radiata Pine. Researchers must design and construct their own dataset, identifying diverse data sources and conducting extensive data collection in various environments to ensure the data’s comprehensiveness and representativeness. The data typically contains highly detailed images and videos, which requires substantial time and effort for labeling and ensuring the accuracy and consistency of these labelings, necessitating rigorous verification processes. In our study, data labeling encompasses several advanced processes, each serving a distinct function to enhance data accuracy and utility. Object detection [95] identifies and localizes branches within images, providing precise bounding boxes around each detected object. Semantic segmentation [12] assigns a class label to every pixel, effectively differentiating branches from the background and other elements in the scene. Instance segmentation [12] further refines this process by distinguishing between individual instances of branches, even within the same class, thereby allowing for more detailed analysis. Depth map generation [46] adds a layer of depth information, supplying a three-dimensional perspective by estimating the distance of each pixel from the camera. These combined labeling techniques are integral for constructing a comprehensive and precise spatial representation of the environment, thereby significantly enhancing the performance and precision of our drone-based pruning system. Object detection, semantic segmentation, and instance segmentation are relatively straightforward, involving marking branches during the labeling process. However, depth map is more challenging as it requires accurate depth information collection. Since we only have the Stereolabs ZED Mini binocular camera which are shown in Figure1.3 and do not have other devices like LiDAR or Structured Light Cameras, we face challenges. Existing depth map datasets, such as KITTI[19], ETH3D[71], and Middlebury[70], are very powerful and widely used in many research areas. These datasets can be used for training and fine-tuning

³<https://www.stereolabs.com/en-nz/store/products/zed-mini>

models; however, it is imperative to create specific Radiata Pine datasets that offer ground truth data to rigorously evaluate the effectiveness and accuracy of the methods. Without this, accurately assessing the dataset is not feasible. Naturally, our camera is constrained by inherent physical challenges, as delineated by its parameters shown in Table 1.1.

Detecting small objects is challenging, while detecting relatively large and distinct objects is more straightforward in current applications[3]. In our project, identifying branches that are only 10mm thick poses significant difficulties. These small targets can easily be obscured or interfered with by other objects in the environment or cluttered backgrounds. Additionally, a 10mm tree branch occupies only a few pixels in the image or video data, demanding high accuracy in image processing and target identification. When inspecting the branches of Radiata Pine, the intertwined branches make it challenging to detect each branch's location and identify the ones that need pruning within a tangle of branches. During drone flights, external factors such as strong winds can cause imbalances, leading to blurred or tilted images captured by the drone's camera. Preprocessing and transforming this data in real-time before detecting the branches is a significant challenge. Sunlight is another external factor that cannot be ignored. Intense light can cause some data captured by the stereo camera to become invalid. Deciding whether to retain and process these data for reuse or discard them directly is another challenge.

Due to the challenge of accurately measuring distances in a dynamic environment, when the drone with the Stereolabs ZED Mini binocular camera detects tree branches, it must precisely measure the distance from the branch to the drone before extending its pruning tool for pruning. Achieving a fast and accurate depth map is challenging due to the complexity of the branches, especially in real-world scenarios like the Radiata Pine, where leaves and overlapping branches can significantly affect measurement accuracy. Traditional algorithms for generating depth maps often encounter matching errors[29]. Although deep neural networks can improve accuracy, the limited GPU computing power of the drone's onboard computers slows down processing, making it impractical for effective deployment. To deploy deep neural network models, we have equipped the system with NVIDIA Jetson devices⁴, but they are expensive, so finding a way to make the algorithm run without upgrading the equipment is also a challenge. Currently, detection and depth assessment are treated as separate and independent tasks, which significantly increases the algorithm's running time. Developing a method to perform these two tasks simultaneously is another challenge to be addressed.

Ultimately, optimizing these models is crucial for enhancing accuracy and reducing inference time. The effective optimization of deep neural network architectures for segmentation and depth evaluation presents a substantial challenge in our research. Neural Architecture Search (NAS) [97] is a technique that automates the design of neural network architectures by using machine learning algorithms to explore a vast space of possible network structures. While NAS offers a promising methodology for creating these architectures, it also introduces a distinct set of challenges that must be addressed. Addressing these challenges is crucial to enhancing the performance and efficiency of models in these complex tasks. These challenges include navigating vast search spaces and handling significant computational costs, which are fundamentally different from the constraints found in traditional manual design methodologies. For instance, FastStereoNet [14] requires substantial resources and time for large datasets and complex tasks, and it still necessitates adjustments for various tasks or hardware platforms despite its reduced search space. The latency-constrained NAS method [87] is efficient but might not perform well across different hardware platforms. Flow NAS [52] shows potential in optical flow estimation but

⁴<https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/autonomous-machines/embedded-systems/>

may need modification for other vision tasks. Hierarchical NAS frameworks [14] excel in deep stereo matching. Methods for generating real-time disparity maps perform well on the KITTI dataset but require validation on other datasets [52]. Consequently, developing a new NAS method tailored specifically to our radiata pine dataset remains a significant challenge to enhance efficiency and applicability.

1.3 Research Goals

The ultimate goal of the research is to develop a new approach to the use of the camera in a drone accurately detecting for tree branches and measuring the distance between the branch and the drone, so that the drone can accurately determine the branch’s position in 3D space and prune it using a robotic knife. Below, we have outlined the research goal into four sub-objectives.

Objective 1: Data Collection and Labelling.

The data will be collected in two scenarios, indoor scenario and outdoor scenario. Since environmental factors such as sunlight affect the quality of the images, it is necessary to collect data indoors and outdoors separately. After data collection, we will pre-process the acquired images to eliminate those that are too blurred or exposed. Next, the filtered images are labeled, including detection and segmentation labeling, as well as depth map labeling, as illustrated in Figure 1.4. Creating an accurate depth map is also a significant issue to consider. Finally, all the data is compiled into an exclusive dataset of Radiata Pine branches for subsequent studies.

- (a) Use the Stereolabs ZED Mini binocular camera to collect images and videos of Radiata Pine branches.

Due to equipment limitations, only the Stereolabs ZED Mini binocular camera is available, and the drone is still under construction. Therefore, indoor data collection involves bringing Radiata Pine branches indoors and photographing them from multiple angles. During this process, factors such as the number of branches, shading, and lighting are adjusted to allow for initial testing and measurement of approximate distances. Once the indoor experiments are complete and the drone is fabricated, the Stereolabs ZED Mini binocular camera is mounted on the drone for outdoor data collection in a commercial Radiata Pine plantation forest to capture images of the branches. The main ZED Mini Camrea Parameters can be seen in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1: ZED Mini Camrea Parameters

Specification				
Focal Length	Default Range	Min Range	Max Range	Baseline
1.4mm	0.2m to 10m	0.1m (0.3ft)	15m (49ft)	63mm
Output Resolution				
Resolution	2x (2208x1242)	2x (1920x1080)	2x (1280x720)	2x (672x376)
Frame rate	15fps	30fps	60fps	100fps

- (b) Image Pre-processing and Data Augmentation for Collected Radiata Pine Branches.

Before proceeding with the labeling of Radiata Pine branches, the collected photo data requires a series of image preprocessing steps. Filters such as median, mean, and Gaussian filters will be explored remove noise and improve image quality[8].

Figure 1.3: ZED Mini Camera

Deblurring algorithms, including blind and non-blind deblurring, reduce blur and clarify the image. Rotation correction ensures the correct orientation of the branches[44]. Color correction adjusts the color balance, contrast, and brightness to maintain true and consistent colors[62][69]. Scale transformation involves scaling, cropping, or filling the image to match the model's input dimensions[9][54]. Data augmentation techniques such as rotating, panning, flipping, scaling, and adding noise generate diverse training samples[63][74][72]. These enhancements increase data diversity, allowing models to generalize better during training. Additionally, we will further refine these methods to optimize image data more effectively. We will also provide a mathematical explanation to illustrate why these methods are effective.

- (c) Subsequently, the Radiata Pine branches in the collected photographs will be labeled.

Since the shape of the tree branches is not regular, the labeled images exhibit irregular geometries. These irregular assemblages are composed of a series of points, with each point's information being labeled and interconnected to form the irregular structure. Simultaneously, well-trained universal segmentation models can be utilized to assist in labeling the branches. Tools such as Segmentation Anything[39] can be employed to pre-label the original photographs, followed by manual precise labeling, which significantly reduces the cost of manpower and time.

- (d) After labeled the branches of the Radiata Pine, it is imperative to determine the distance between the branches by generating a depth map.

There are several methods to obtain accurate depth maps, including Multi-View Stereo Photography[91], Laser Detection and Ranging[94][43], and Time-of-Flight cameras[18]. However, since only a stereo camera is available, it is necessary to explore how to obtain sufficiently accurate depth maps through stereo photography. Due to device limitations, plans include training and fine-tuning the dataset using advanced methods such as NeRF[80] or 3DGS[36] with many publicly available depth estimation datasets to obtain better depth maps. Then, these depth maps are processed to make them as close as possible to the ground-truth depth maps. Finally, the raw data, processed data, labeled data, and depth maps are consolidated into a dataset for future research purposes.

Figure 1.4: The process flowchart for Objectives 1 and 2. The steps “Use ZED Mini to collect data” and “Image preprocessing and data augmentation” correspond to Objective 1, while the remaining steps pertain to Objective 2.

Objective 2: Tree Branch Detection and Distance Estimation.

This process is divided into three parts. The first part involves utilizing the camera to detect the location of a circular area around each branch. The second part focuses on generating a depth map to capture the three-dimensional spatial information of the scene. In the third part, branches are detected, and by correlating the detected branches with the depth map, the precise distances from the camera to each branch are determined. Figure 1.4 outlines the overall process. Ultimately, we will implement these three steps sequentially and apply them to a drone for testing.

- (a) A neural network architecture will be developed to accurately detect irregular branches.

Since the branches are irregular, the requirement is not for their edge position in the form of a traditional box, but for sufficiently clear information to detect the circular region around the branches, allowing precise identification of the required details. Traditional segmentation methods like Canny Edge Detection[10] and Active Contours[34] can be used; however, in extremely complex environments where branches are highly chaotic, these methods may fall short. Therefore, a neural network architecture, such as U-Net[67], Mask R-CNN[26] and YOLO[32], will be selected and developed to train and obtain a robust segmentation model. This model will achieve not only detect the location of the branches but also provide detailed edge information, ensuring precise segmentation even in complicated scenarios.

- (b) The depth map of the Radiata Pine branches will be obtained.

In addition to acquiring the edge information of the branches, obtaining a depth map is crucial for accurately measuring the distance from the branches to the drone. Given the equipment constraints, stereo cameras are employed to generate the depth maps, providing the necessary spatial data for precise distance estimation. Traditional methods such as Multi-Window Matching Filtering[28], Belief Propagation[77], Graph Cuts[31], and Semi-Global Block Matching[28] can be utilized. Alternatively, neural network architectures like PSMNet[11] and GWCNet[24] can be employed to train models and predict the depth maps of the branches. The performance of conventional depth estimation techniques will be compared with neural network predictions in terms of speed and accuracy. Based on this evaluation, the most effective method will be selected for the final implementation.

- (c) Develop a method for integrating edge information and depth map data accurately to determine branch distance.

With both the edge information of the branches and the depth map data available, the subsequent objective is to develop a novel approach that integrates these two information sources to accurately determine the distance between the camera and the pixels corresponding to the branches. This study will explore both linear and parallel methods of integration, systematically comparing their performance in terms of detection accuracy and processing speed to identify the most effective approach.

- (d) Optimising the developed algorithms and apply the best method to the drone for testing.

The algorithms are optimized and integrated into the drone, combining them with the drone's robotic knife for testing to assess the accuracy of branch pruning. The resulting model is applied to the drone to evaluate its take-off and pruning capabilities.

Objective 3: Interpretable models and Optimisation for Better Accuracy.

To address this issue and enhance the transparency of the depth map generation process, we propose to focus on the Semi-Global Block Matching (SGBM). SGBM offers greater interpretability owing to its dependence on a variety of parameters that critically influence the quality of the resulting depth maps [28]. To optimize these parameters, we suggest employing the Enlightenment Algorithm [57] to determine the optimal configurations across diverse datasets, aiming for more accurate depth maps, particularly in the analysis of tree branches. By generating depth maps using different parameter settings and analyzing the results, this approach seeks not only to improve depth map quality but also to better understand the parameter sensitivity and optimization strategies of the SGBM algorithm.

- (a) Provide an explanation and analysis of how each parameter affects the performance of the SGBM algorithm in generating the depth map.

The effectiveness of the SGBM algorithm in stereo vision and depth estimation depends on several key parameters, such as block size, number of disparities, and penalty values for disparity changes (P1 and P2) [28]. Among these, Block size is crucial for balancing noise suppression and detail preservation. The number of disparities determines the depth range and affects computational load. Penalty values P1 and P2 regulate the smoothness of the disparity map, with P1 handling minor changes and P2 managing larger jumps, maintaining a balance between noise reduction and edge preservation. The mode of operation influences the trade-off between computational efficiency and the accuracy of the depth map.

- (b) These parameters of the SGBM will be optimized by the heuristic algorithm to achieve relatively optimal results across different data sets.

Once the meaning and role of these parameters are understood, they are encoded and decoded to fit techniques such as Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) [16] [76] and Genetic Algorithms (GA) [17]. Additionally, Genetic Programming (GP) [59] is employed to compare with SGBM, aiming to develop interpretable models. The minimization objective function is then defined to obtain the optimal parameters. These optimized parameters are initially tested on datasets such as KITTI, ETH3D, and Middlebury, where ground truth is known, allowing for verification of the optimal parameters across different datasets. Finally, these optimal parameters are used with the SGBM algorithm to test and analyze the Radiata Pine branches dataset.

- (c) The most suitable post-processing filter will be identified and applied to SGBM to make the depth map clearer.

The SGBM algorithm is optimized by enhancing the cost function using techniques like Adaptive Weights[92], which utilize adaptive weighting schemes to better handle varying lighting conditions and textures, and Census Transform[93], which is less sensitive to lighting changes and noise. Additionally, pre-processing steps such as image rectification and noise reduction, as well as post-processing steps like disparity refinement, consistency checks, and hole filling, are improved. SGBM is also combined with deep learning-based approaches to leverage the strengths of both techniques, further enhancing the algorithm’s performance and accuracy. These enhancements are tested on public datasets such as KITTI, ETH3D, and Middlebury, and are applied to the Radiata Pine branches dataset to evaluate their effectiveness.

Objective 4: Image Segmentation and Optimisation for Resource Efficiency

The depth estimation model is then integrated with the segmentation model to enhance overall performance. To ensure efficient drone operation, computational performance is optimized by reducing processing time and resource usage without sacrificing accuracy. This enables real-time deployment on drones for precise and efficient branch detection and positioning for pruning.

- (a) Achieving instance segmentation model on the Radiata Pine branches dataset.

To evaluate and select an optimal instance segmentation model for high-precision scenarios, several popular models are compared, including Mask R-CNN[26], YOLACT[7], SOLOv2[83], Panoptic FPN[38], CenterMask[49], DeepLab[13], and YOLO[66]. These models are assessed based on accuracy, speed, and application suitability, and are subsequently tested on the Radiata Pine branches dataset to determine the most effective segmentation model.

- (b) Developing an automated framework utilizing one-shot NAS for instance segmentation.

To reduce the computational cost of individual fitness evaluations, the automated framework employs one-shot NAS for instance segmentation by inheriting weights from the supernet. Evolutionary computation methods will be built to search key network components: the backbone, feature pyramid model, and network head within a unified pipeline. This method not only searches for structures within blocks but also explores connections between blocks. To achieve this, a large, integrated supernet is designed first, with specialized options for its components. Promising sub-networks can then be searched from the well-designed and pre-trained supernet, leading to the following two sub-objectives.

- (c) Combine the segmentation model with the depth map and compare various combinations to determine the optimal one based on speed and accuracy.

There are two primary methods for integrating these models. The first method is linear: when the ZED Mini camera captures data of the branches, we first perform segmentation and then depth evaluation, or vice versa. This sequential process is linear. The second method involves multitask[35][47] approaches designed to handle images more effectively, enabling simultaneous segmentation and depth evaluation. Unlike multimodal[64][37] methods that process different types of data, our goal is

to process the same pair of stereo images for both segmentation and depth evaluation. By comparing these two approaches, we aim to identify which method is faster and more accurate.

1.4 Organization of Proposal

The remainder of this proposal is organized as follows. Chapter 2 presents the essential background on image segmentation, depth mapping, monocular depth estimation, stereo depth estimation, machine learning, convolutional neural network, and evolutionary computation algorithms, discussing relevant literature. Chapter 3 outlines preliminary work on branch instance segmentation and obtaining the branch's depth map, which is combined to measure the distance between the branch and the camera. Chapter 4 details the research plan and provides a timeline of the project's tasks. The following Figure 1.5 is the flow chart of this research.

Figure 1.5: Research flowchart

Chapter 2

Literature Review

This chapter reviews the literature on image segmentation and depth map generation as approaches to detecting Radiata Pine branches and measuring their distance from the camera. It covers essential background and concepts in image segmentation and depth estimation, particularly in the context of deep learning methods. The chapter also reviews related work in combining these techniques, using both traditional and modern approaches for tree branch detection and distance measurement.

2.1 Computer Vision Overview

Computer vision involves several interconnected tasks aimed at enabling machines to interpret and understand visual data. The process often begins with image preprocessing, where techniques like noise reduction and intensity normalization improve image quality for subsequent analysis [22]. This step is followed by image segmentation, which divides an image into meaningful regions, simplifying the identification and localization of objects [61]. Object detection then builds on this by identifying and classifying objects within the segmented areas, a crucial function in fields like autonomous systems and medical diagnostics. Complementing these tasks, feature extraction identifies key visual attributes that support classification and recognition [54]. Depth estimation further enhances understanding by inferring the spatial relationships and distances between objects in a scene, enabling applications that require 3D perception [70]. Lastly, object tracking ensures continuous monitoring of objects as they move across frames, supporting dynamic tasks such as surveillance and activity analysis [6].

2.2 Machine Learning

2.2.1 Overview

Machine learning (ML) has significantly advanced the field of computer vision, driven by developments in big data analytics and computational capabilities. ML, a subfield of artificial intelligence (AI), aims to develop algorithms that learn from data and improve their predictive performance or decision-making autonomously. Its impact is evident in applications such as object detection, image segmentation, and depth estimation, which are critical for tasks such as tree branch detection in natural environments.

Machine learning methodologies in computer vision can be broadly categorized into supervised learning, unsupervised learning, and reinforcement learning. Supervised learning has shown remarkable success in tasks like semantic segmentation and object detection,

where models are trained on labeled datasets to identify features such as branches or leaves in complex images. Popular algorithms include convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and U-Net architectures, widely used for pixel-level classification and segmentation tasks [68]. Unsupervised learning, often used for clustering or dimensionality reduction, helps identify underlying structures in image data without labeled samples, with applications in tasks like anomaly detection in forest environments [89]. Reinforcement learning is also being explored for robotic applications, such as enabling drones to navigate autonomously while detecting tree branches and estimating their depth [96].

Recent research has increasingly focused on using deep learning techniques for tasks such as tree branch detection and depth estimation. For example, stereo vision-based approaches leverage ML to generate accurate depth maps, which are critical for pruning applications [11]. The integration of these methods with techniques such as disparity map generation and post-processing filters like weighted least squares (WLS) has further improved accuracy in natural environments [30]. Future research directions emphasize developing robust and interpretable models that can handle real-time processing in outdoor conditions, pushing the boundaries of tree branch detection and image segmentation for practical applications in forestry and environmental monitoring.

These evolving research areas seek to integrate machine learning models with drone systems to enhance tree management, fundamentally transforming traditional methods of forest monitoring and maintenance.

2.2.2 Convolutional Neural Networks

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and their variants have become a fundamental tool for most state-of-the-art image recognition and computer vision applications due to their ability to automatically learn spatial hierarchies of features from images. CNNs are specifically designed for processing structured grid data, such as images, and consist of key components including convolutional layers, pooling layers, and fully connected layers, each contributing to the network's learning capabilities [48, 45, 27].

The convolutional layer is the core building block of CNNs, performing a mathematical operation called convolution. This involves sliding a filter (or kernel) over the input data to capture local dependencies and extract features such as edges, textures, and patterns. The resulting feature maps represent the presence of these features across various spatial locations in the input image. Pooling layers are subsequently used to reduce the spatial dimensions of feature maps, helping to lower computational complexity and mitigate overfitting. Max pooling and average pooling are the most common pooling operations, with max pooling selecting the maximum value in each region and average pooling computing the average value [75].

Fully connected (FC) layers, positioned at the end of the CNN architecture, are similar to traditional neural network layers where each neuron is connected to every neuron in the previous layer. These layers combine the spatially distributed features learned by the convolutional and pooling layers to perform high-level reasoning for classification or regression tasks. The output from the convolutional or pooling layers is flattened into a one-dimensional vector before being passed to the fully connected layers, where non-linear activation functions such as ReLU or softmax produce the final output [23].

CNNs and their variants, such as ResNet [27], VGG [75], and Inception [78], leverage the hierarchical structure of image data, with convolutional layers capturing local patterns, pooling layers reducing dimensionality, and fully connected layers integrating features for predictions. These variants introduce innovations like skip connections, deeper architectures, and multiple scales of feature extraction, which enhance performance and address

challenges like vanishing gradients. This architecture makes CNNs highly effective for tasks such as image recognition and object detection. As deep learning research progresses, CNNs and their variants continue to evolve and remain essential in the field of machine learning [27, 45].

2.2.3 Evolutionary Computation Algorithm

This subsection discusses key evolutionary computation techniques used for optimization tasks, including Genetic Programming (GP), Genetic Algorithms (GA), and Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO).

2.2.3.1 Genetic Programming(GP)

Genetic Programming (GP)[1] is a powerful evolutionary computation technique designed to automatically evolve programs for solving complex problems. By starting with a population of randomly generated programs, GP iteratively refines them through genetic operations such as reproduction, crossover, and mutation [42, 4]. Each program's performance is assessed using a fitness function, and higher-performing programs are selected for further evolution, progressively yielding better solutions. GP has been successfully applied to a wide range of fields, and in the context of computer vision, it can be employed for image feature extraction [15] and optimization of parameters in algorithms like Semi-Global Block Matching (SGBM), enhancing the accuracy of disparity map generation [84, 30].

2.2.3.2 Genetic Algorithms(GA)

Genetic Algorithms (GA) are evolutionary computation methods inspired by natural selection. They evolve a population of potential solutions using selection, crossover, and mutation over successive generations. Key components include chromosome representation, fitness evaluation, and genetic operators. Variants like multiobjective GA (MOGA), parallel GA, chaotic GA, and hybrid GA have been developed to address specific optimization challenges. GA are widely applied in areas such as operations management, multimedia, and wireless networking, showcasing their effectiveness in complex optimization tasks.

2.2.3.3 Particle Swarm Optimization(PSO)

Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) is an optimization algorithm inspired by the social behavior of flocks. It utilizes particle interactions within a swarm to optimize solutions, with enhancements like hybrid algorithms, adaptive parameter adjustments, and learning-based improvements. PSO is broadly applied in fields such as healthcare, environmental monitoring, industrial applications, and smart cities. Future research aims to develop more efficient hybrid algorithms, improve parameter adjustment strategies, and explore new application areas to tackle large-scale and dynamic optimization challenges.

2.3 Image Segmentation

In the field of image segmentation, methodologies are generally divided into semantic segmentation and instance segmentation. Semantic segmentation assigns a class label to every pixel in an image, enabling a comprehensive understanding of scene components such as "tree" or "ground." However, it does not distinguish between different instances of the same class, treating all similar objects as a single entity.

Figure 2.1: Flowchart of Genetic Algorithm Process

Instance segmentation, by contrast, not only categorizes pixels but also differentiates between individual instances of the same class. This task combines object detection and segmentation, identifying the object’s category and distinguishing specific instances. Advances in deep learning have propelled this field, with models like Mask R-CNN achieving notable success by leveraging region proposal networks along with pixel-wise segmentation.

Our work leverages instance segmentation to differentiate between branches on the same Radiata Pine tree, enabling precise identification of branch positions. This differentiation is crucial for automated pruning applications, where accurately distinguishing individual branches is essential for precise cutting and effective tree management.

2.3.1 Mask R-CNN

Mask R-CNN, an extension of Faster R-CNN, is widely used for object detection and instance segmentation tasks. It enhances Faster R-CNN by adding a branch for predicting segmentation masks for each detected object, making it effective for applications requiring both bounding box detection and pixel-level segmentation. Numerous studies have utilized Mask R-CNN for tasks such as scene understanding, medical image analysis, and object localization due to its high accuracy and flexibility [26].

2.3.2 YOLO

YOLO (You Only Look Once) is a popular real-time object detection algorithm known for its speed and efficiency. Unlike traditional methods, YOLO frames object detection as a single regression problem, predicting bounding boxes and class probabilities directly from the entire image in one forward pass. Various versions of YOLO (v2, v3, v4) have been employed in applications ranging from autonomous driving to surveillance due to their balance between detection accuracy and computational efficiency [66]. More recent versions, such as

YOLOv8 and YOLOv9, have introduced improvements in both speed and precision, particularly for tasks involving instance segmentation. YOLOv8 and YOLOv9 further enhance segmentation accuracy and performance in real-time applications, making them suitable for tasks requiring both object detection and precise mask generation.

2.3.3 U-Net

U-Net is a fully convolutional neural network originally designed for biomedical image segmentation. Its U-shaped architecture, with symmetric encoder-decoder paths and skip connections, allows for precise localization and segmentation of features even with a limited amount of training data. U-Net has been widely adapted in a variety of domains beyond medical imaging, such as satellite image segmentation, cell tracking, and agricultural monitoring, due to its ability to generate accurate segmentation maps with high spatial resolution [67].

2.4 Depth Map

Depth map generation [46] is also another crucial aspect of computer vision, enabling the inference of a scene’s three-dimensional structure from one or more images. In our drone application, equipped with a stereo camera, depth maps are obtained from two distinct viewpoints. For precise pruning of branches using a pruning tool mounted on the drone, accurately identifying the tree branches and determining their distance from the drone is essential.

Depth map, representing the distance from each pixel in the image to the camera, are generated using either active or passive methods. Active methods employ sensors that emit and receive signals to measure depth, including technologies such as LiDAR, structured light[86], and time-of-flight cameras[41]. Conversely, passive methods rely on existing optical information, utilizing techniques such as stereo matching[82], multi-view geometry, and monocular depth estimation[25].

Since the drone is equipped exclusively with a stereo camera, the methodology is inherently constrained to the use of one or two cameras. Consequently, stereo matching generates depth maps by deriving values through triangulation, leveraging the parallax effect between the cameras. To further elucidate this process, we will proceed with a mathematical formulation to offer a more rigorous and precise explanation of how depth maps are generated using stereo vision.[25] In a stereo vision system, the intrinsic camera parameters and image coordinates allow us to determine the physical properties of the scene. Let the focal lengths of the camera along the x-axis and y-axis be denoted as f_x and f_y , respectively. The parameters o_x and o_y represent the horizontal and vertical offsets of the image center from the top-left corner of the camera’s image sensor. Specifically, o_x refers to the horizontal displacement from the left edge of the sensor to the optical center’s projection, while o_y indicates the vertical displacement from the top edge of the sensor to the same point.

Based on previous work[79], we can summarize that (1) and (2) describe the position of pixel point (u_l, v_l) in the left camera view, while (3) and (4) describe the position of pixel point (u_r, v_r) in the right camera view.

$$u_l = f_x \frac{x}{z} + o_x \quad (2.1)$$

$$v_l = f_y \frac{y}{z} + o_y \quad (2.2)$$

Figure 2.2: Triangulation using Two Cameras to Obtain the Depth Map. The point (u_l, v_l) represents the projection of point $p(x, y, z)$ in three-dimensional space onto the image plane of the left camera, whereas point (u_r, v_r) corresponds to the projection of the same point onto the right camera's image plane. The variable b denotes the baseline distance separating the left and right cameras. \hat{x} , \hat{y} , and \hat{z} represent the three axes of the camera or world coordinate frame, corresponding to the x , y , and z directions.

$$u_r = f_x \frac{x - b}{z} + o_x \quad (2.3)$$

$$v_r = f_y \frac{y}{z} + o_y \quad (2.4)$$

Combining (1) and (2), as well as (3) and (4), we can obtain its pixel coordinates as (5).

$$\begin{aligned} (u_l, v_l) &= (f_x \frac{x}{z} + o_x, f_y \frac{y}{z} + o_y) \\ (u_r, v_r) &= (f_x \frac{x - b}{z} + o_x, f_y \frac{y}{z} + o_y) \end{aligned} \quad (2.5)$$

Based on the pixel coordinates of the left and right cameras, we can find the coordinates of the object in three dimensions (x, y, z) .

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \frac{b(u_l - o_x)}{(u_l - u_r)} \\ y &= \frac{bf_x(v_l - o_y)}{f_y(u_l - u_r)} \\ z &= \frac{bf_x}{(u_l - u_r)} \end{aligned} \quad (2.6)$$

After that, the formulae for disparity value and depth value.

$$\text{Disparity} : d = u_l - u_r \quad (2.7)$$

$$\text{Depth} : z = \frac{bf_x}{(u_l - u_r)} \quad (2.8)$$

Let the product of the baseline b and the focal length of the camera in the x -direction f_x to a fixed constant W .

$$W = b \cdot f_x \quad (2.9)$$

Substituting W into (9), we get a more concise (10).

$$z = \frac{W}{d} \tag{2.10}$$

Since W is a fixed constant, and z and d are inversely proportional, the larger the disparity value, the smaller the depth value. In other words, a larger disparity value indicates that the pixel point is closer to the camera.

2.5 Monocular Depth Estimation

Monocular depth estimation is a challenging computer vision task that seeks to predict depth information from a single image. Unlike stereo vision, which derives depth from two or more viewpoints, monocular depth estimation must infer the scene’s geometric structure from just one perspective, without explicit depth cues. This requires advanced learning algorithms and various priors to infer depth from monocular cues such as texture gradients, object sizes, occlusions, and perspective. In this section, we discuss two recent methods, MiDaS and Depth Anything, that address these challenges.

2.5.1 MiDaS

MiDaS[65] presents a robust approach to monocular depth estimation, emphasizing model generalization across diverse environments. The authors introduce novel loss functions that mitigate incompatibilities between datasets, such as inconsistent or unknown depth ranges. These loss functions enable training on data from various sensing modalities, including stereo cameras, laser scanners, and structured light sensors, regardless of calibration quality. Moreover, MiDaS evaluates existing datasets and proposes strategies for optimal dataset mixing during training, employing a principled multi-objective optimization approach to achieve superior outcomes compared to naive mixing techniques. A key contribution is the use of high-capacity encoders pretrained on large-scale auxiliary tasks, which significantly enhances performance.

Extensive experiments, involving approximately six GPU months of computation, demonstrate that training on a diverse set of images with a suitable training procedure results in state-of-the-art performance across multiple environments. MiDaS validates this through zero-shot cross-dataset transfer experiments, training on certain datasets while testing on unseen ones, showing that this approach serves as a more reliable proxy for real-world performance than conventional methods of training and testing on subsets of the same dataset.

2.5.2 Depth Anything

Depth Anything[90] builds upon existing depth estimation methods by utilizing a pseudo-labeling and teacher-student architecture to overcome current limitations in the field. It generates depth labels for 62 million initially unlabeled images from eight public datasets using a pre-trained monocular depth model, thereby creating a diverse pseudo-labeled dataset. The teacher model, trained on labeled datasets, generates pseudo labels that are combined with real labeled data to train a student model, enhancing the model’s generalization capabilities.

To further improve robustness, Depth Anything employs strong data augmentations, such as color jittering, Gaussian blurring, and CutMix. Additionally, auxiliary supervision is provided using semantic priors from pre-trained encoders, aligning with the current trend of leveraging multi-task learning to boost depth estimation performance.

Evaluations on multiple public datasets, including NYUv2 and KITTI, demonstrate the effectiveness of Depth Anything, achieving state-of-the-art results in relative depth estimation. This approach also lays a strong foundation for downstream tasks such as metric depth estimation and semantic segmentation, highlighting its versatility and utility in broader computer vision applications.

2.6 Stereo Depth Estimation

Stereo depth estimation has seen the development of numerous methods in computer vision, each providing different advantages depending on the application. This research reviews several widely adopted techniques, including Block Matching (BM), Semi-Global Block Matching (SGBM), Attention Concatenation Volume Network (ACVNet), Group-wise Correlation Network (GWCNet), MobileStereoNet, Pyramid Stereo Matching Network (PSM-Net), Recurrent All-Pairs Field Transforms Stereo (RAFT-Stereo), and Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF)

2.6.1 Block Matching(BM)

In Block Matching (BM)[40][21], a region from one image is selected as a reference template, and the corresponding region is located in the other image by searching for the area with the highest similarity. This similarity is commonly assessed by comparing pixel intensities between the two regions. The difference in position between these matched regions, known as disparity, serves as the key to estimating depth in the scene. An example of this process is illustrated in Figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3: Block Matching example, the L means the Template Window, the T means the Search Scan Line, we set the Left Camera Image be fix E_l , and find the correlative pixel in the Right Camera Image E_r

2.6.2 Semi-Global Block Matching (SGBM)

Semi-Global Block Matching (SGBM)[29] is a widely used method for depth estimation that enhances traditional block matching by minimizing global energy through multi-directional cost aggregation. It begins by computing matching costs for each pixel across a range of disparities using techniques like Absolute Difference (AD) or Mutual Information (MI). These costs are then aggregated along multiple paths, ensuring smoothness across the image while

maintaining computational efficiency. The disparity with the lowest aggregated cost is selected for each pixel, followed by sub-pixel refinement to increase precision. Post-processing techniques such as left-right consistency checks, uniqueness constraints, and speckle filtering are applied to refine the disparity map and eliminate errors. These steps help SGBM generate accurate depth maps, making it suitable for applications requiring a balance between precision and efficiency, such as autonomous driving and 3D scene reconstruction.

2.6.3 ACVNet

ACVNet[88] introduces a novel cost volume construction method called Attention Concatenation Volume (ACV) for efficient and accurate stereo matching. ACV generates attention weights to filter redundant information in the concatenation volume, enhancing matching-related information. Based on ACV, the authors designed a highly accurate stereo matching network called ACVNet, and a real-time version called ACVNet-Fast. ACVNet demonstrates superior performance and strong generalization abilities across multiple benchmarks, including Scene Flow, KITTI 2012, KITTI 2015, and ETH3D datasets.

The ACVNet architecture comprises four main modules: feature extraction, attention concatenation volume construction, cost aggregation, and disparity prediction. The feature extraction uses a three-level ResNet-like architecture to generate feature maps, which are then used to create attention weights. The ACV construction involves three steps: initial concatenation volume construction, attention weight generation, and attention filtering. The generated attention weights filter the initial concatenation volume to form a 4D cost volume. The cost aggregation module processes this volume using stacked 3D hourglass networks, and the disparity prediction module generates the final disparity map.

Figure 2.4: AVCNet Architecture for Stereo Vision Depth Estimation [88]

2.6.4 GWCNet

GwcNet[24], a novel stereo matching network that estimates disparity maps using group-wise correlation to construct the cost volume. Unlike traditional methods that use full correlation or concatenation, GwcNet splits features into groups and calculates correlations for each group separately, combining these into a 4D cost volume. This approach retains rich feature information and improves similarity measures. The network also includes an improved 3D aggregation module with stacked hourglass networks, enhancing performance and reducing inference time. Experiments on Scene Flow, KITTI 2012, and KITTI 2015

datasets show that GwcNet outperforms previous methods in accuracy and efficiency, making it suitable for applications like autonomous driving and robot navigation.

2.6.5 mobileStereoNet

MobileStereoNet[73], which aims to address the high computational cost of deep learning in stereo matching. The authors propose two lightweight models: a 2D model and a 3D model, designed using 2D and 3D MobileNet blocks, respectively. These models employ an encoder-decoder architecture for feature extraction and disparity estimation. Specifically, the study introduces a novel cost volume construction method that enhances the accuracy of the 2D model through interlacing, making its performance close to that of the 3D model. Experimental results demonstrate that these models significantly reduce computational costs (in terms of parameters and operations) while maintaining high accuracy, making them particularly suitable for deployment on resource-constrained embedded devices.

2.6.6 PSMNet

Pyramid Stereo Matching Network (PSMNet)[11], designed to enhance stereo image matching by leveraging global context information. PSMNet consists of two main modules: the Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP) module and the 3D Convolutional Neural Network (3D CNN). The SPP module aggregates context information at different scales and locations to form a cost volume, while the 3D CNN uses multiple stacked hourglass networks with intermediate supervision to regularize these cost volumes. PSMNet has demonstrated superior performance on the KITTI 2012 and 2015 benchmark datasets, ranking at the top of these leaderboards. Experiments show that PSMNet achieves higher accuracy and stability in challenging areas such as occlusions, repeated patterns, textureless regions, and reflective surfaces.

Figure 2.5: PSMNet Architecture for Stereo Vision Depth Estimation [11]

2.6.7 RAFT-Stereo

“RAFT-Stereo: Multilevel Recurrent Field Transforms for Stereo Matching”[53] introduces a new deep learning architecture called RAFT-Stereo for rectified stereo matching. This approach is based on the RAFT optical flow network and utilizes multi-level convolutional GRUs to efficiently propagate information across images. Unlike existing stereo networks, RAFT-Stereo employs only 2D convolutions and a lightweight cost volume, avoiding the high computational cost of 3D convolutions, which allows it to be directly applied to high-resolution images.

RAFT-Stereo demonstrates superior performance on the Middlebury and ETH3D benchmarks and excels in cross-dataset generalization. By adopting GRU units at multiple resolutions and updating hidden states layer by layer, it achieves efficient real-time inference suitable for various practical applications. The code is publicly available on GitHub, further advancing research and applications in the field of stereo matching.

Figure 2.6: RAFT-Stereo Architecture for Stereo Vision Depth Estimation [53]

2.6.8 NeRF

NeRF[80] introduces a novel framework for training deep stereo networks without real ground-truth data, leveraging state-of-the-art neural rendering techniques to generate stereo training data from image sequences captured with a single handheld camera. The framework addresses occlusions by rendering stereo triplets and using depth maps as proxy labels, enabling stereo networks to predict sharp and detailed disparity maps. Experimental results show a 30-40% improvement over existing self-supervised methods on the challenging Middlebury dataset, often outperforming supervised models in zero-shot generalization. The process involves collecting sparse multi-view images from static scenes with a handheld camera, using COLMAP to estimate camera intrinsics and poses, training independent NeRF models to render stereo triplets and depth maps, and generating virtual stereo camera extrinsics to create stereo pairs and triplets. The rendered image triplets are then used to train stereo networks through photometric reconstruction and disparity losses. This method effectively addresses occlusions and fine detail issues in self-supervised learning, achieving outstanding zero-shot generalization performance and providing a low-cost, scalable approach to stereo depth estimation research without the need for real stereo cameras or ground-truth labels.

Figure 2.7: Nerf Method for Stereo Vision Depth Estimation [80]

2.7 Summary

This chapter reviewed essential techniques for tree branch detection and depth estimation, focusing on methods like ACVNet, RAFT-Stereo, PSMNet, and NeRF to enhance stereo vision. ACVNet utilizes attention-based cost volumes for efficient stereo matching, while RAFT-Stereo refines disparities iteratively. PSMNet employs spatial pyramid pooling to capture multiscale context, and NeRF generates synthetic stereo triplets from single-camera sequences, providing proxy depth labels for improved accuracy. Additionally, the chapter examined interpretable models and optimization techniques, such as GAs, PSO, and GP, which were used to optimize SGBM parameters for faster and more accurate depth estimation.

Chapter 3

Preliminary Work

In this chapter, we present the process from data collection and image instance segmentation to the application of both traditional and deep learning techniques for branch detection and depth map generation. By integrating these approaches, we aim to achieve accurate detection of tree branches and estimate their distances using only a single stereo vision camera. The entire workflow is illustrated in Fig.3.1.

Figure 3.1: Overview of the Method

3.1 Methods

we presents the process from data collection and image instance segmentation to the application of both traditional and deep learning techniques for branch detection and depth map generation. By integrating these approaches, we aim to achieve accurate detection of tree branches and estimate their distances using only a single stereo vision camera.

3.1.1 Data Collection and Image Instance Segmentation for Tree Branch Plane Localization

In this research, we primarily collected indoor data using a ZED Mini camera¹, capturing images from different corners of the laboratory at a resolution of 1920×1080. We photographed various tree branches under different lighting conditions to avoid over-idealization of the training images. So far, we have collected 61 pairs of photos (i.e., 122 images) for the training dataset and another 10 pairs for the test dataset.

After collecting the data, our process began with image labeling, specifically annotating the points around each branch. This step was essential for accurate segmentation. Given the relatively small size of the dataset, it was critical to perform robust model testing to check the feasibility of our approach. We initiated our experiments using Mask R-CNN, employing several backbone architectures such as ResNet-50, ResNet-101, and ResNeXt-101-32×8d. These models varied in complexity and were chosen to explore different trade-offs between speed and accuracy. The Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) and Dilated-C5 (DC5) architectures were also evaluated to assess their performance in generating masks and predicting bounding boxes. A comprehensive analysis of the accuracy results will be presented in the 3.2.1 section.

3.1.2 SGBM for Generating Depth Map

SGBM optimizes the matching cost by aggregating information across multiple directions. This semi-global approach enhances accuracy and consistency by mitigating errors in textureless regions and around sharp object boundaries, resulting in a more refined and coherent disparity map. To further improve the output, Weighted Least Squares (WLS) post-processing was applied to smooth the disparity map while preserving critical edge details. The final disparity map was then converted into a depth map using Equation (10), with the corresponding results discussed in the 3.2.2 section.

3.1.3 Deep learning Methods for Generating Depth Map

Compared to traditional algorithms, deep learning methods for generating depth maps primarily focus on two areas: monocular depth estimation and stereo depth estimation. In the field of monocular depth estimation, two leading models are MiDaS[65] and Depth Anything[90]. MiDaS employs transformer-based backbones such as BEiT, Swin, and SwinV2, trained on large, diverse datasets using a scale-and-shift-invariant loss function, enabling robust cross-dataset zero-shot inference. In contrast, Depth Anything leverages vast amounts of unlabeled data while retaining rich semantic priors from pre-trained models. This approach allows Depth Anything to excel in zero-shot depth estimation and serve as a robust foundation for metric depth estimation. We directly applied MiDaS and Depth Anything to our own dataset to observe its prediction results.

In the domain of stereo depth estimation, widely used methods include ACVNet [88], GwcNet [24], PSMNet [11], MobileStereoNet [73], and RAFTNet [53]. These methods leverage advanced neural network architectures to achieve high-quality depth estimation by effectively capturing disparity information from stereo images. In parallel, NeRF represent 3D scenes as continuous volumetric radiance fields using a neural network that models spatial positions and viewing directions, outputting color and density values. NeRF uses volumetric rendering to generate high-quality images from novel viewpoints by accumulating color and density along rays, optimizing the scene representation by minimizing differences with

¹<https://store.stereolabs.com/products/zed-mini>

ground-truth images. Furthermore, NeRF incorporates positional encoding and hierarchical sampling to capture high-frequency details and improve rendering efficiency, making it capable of photorealistic novel view synthesis of complex scenes.

In the proposed method, we aim to select the optimal stereo depth estimation network from ACVNet, GwcNet, PSMNet, MobileStereoNet, and RAFTNet to be integrated with NeRF. The goal is to leverage the advantages of the selected depth estimation method for generating accurate depth maps.

In our research, we utilized several stereo matching datasets, such as KITTI [19] and Scene Flow [56], to evaluate and test the performance of all these models. Each model architecture was fine-tuning on these datasets to enhance adaptability and robustness across different real-world scenarios. This comprehensive testing approach was chosen to determine the most effective models for stereo depth estimation, particularly for radiata pine branch detection, thereby guiding the selection of suitable techniques for our application.

We examined the impact of fine-tuning on depth map predictions using PSMNet as a representative model. We first used the pretrained model on three datasets: KITTI2012, KITTI2015, and Scene Flow to predict the branch dataset. The models pretrained on KITTI2012 and KITTI2015 were then fine-tuned for an additional 100 epochs to generate branch depth maps. Due to the absence of ground-truth data for precise quantitative evaluation, we assessed the accuracy of depth predictions around tree branches by visually inspecting the clarity of pixel depth information. The comparative experimental results are presented and discussed in Section 3.2.2.

3.1.4 Integration of Image Instance Segmentation and Depth Map Generation

The ultimate objective is to enable the stereo camera mounted on the drone to simultaneously perform instance segmentation and depth estimation in order to precisely determine the spatial positions of tree branches. To achieve this, it is necessary to integrate the segmentation model and the depth map generation method.

In Fig. 3.10, we begin by applying a segmentation model to extract information about the points surrounding the tree branches. These points are subsequently connected to form a continuous surface, with the coordinates of all points within this surface mapped to their corresponding locations on the depth map. Consequently, the depth values of all pixels on the branches are determined. Statistical analysis is then performed, and the final distance between the camera and the branches is calculated by averaging the depth values from the range where the pixel density is highest.

(a) Predicted Points Spaced at a Certain Distance (b) Depth Map Generated Using SGBM and WLS Filter

Figure 3.2: (a) Shows the predicted points spaced a certain distance apart, and (b) displays the depth map obtained from SGBM. Combining these allows for determining the final distance between the branches and the stereo camera.

3.1.5 Performance Metrics

In assessing the performance of the object detection and segmentation model, two critical metrics must be considered: computational efficiency (measured by running time) and accuracy. For object detection and segmentation, accuracy is evaluated using mAP_{50-95} (Mean Average Precision at Intersection over Union thresholds ranging from 50% to 95%). For the depth estimation component, accuracy is measured using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) to quantify the depth prediction error.

Let $AP(t)$ denote the Average Precision at a specific IoU threshold t , where t represents the IoU threshold varying from 0.5 to 0.95 in increments of 0.05. The variable n denotes the total number of IoU thresholds considered, typically 10[50]. The formula for mAP_{50-95} is given by:

$$mAP_{50-95} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{t=0.5}^{0.95} AP(t) \quad (3.1)$$

Furthermore, let n as the total number of data points, where y_i denotes the actual value and \hat{y}_i represents the predicted value[2]. The formula for the RMSE is given by:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (3.2)$$

3.2 Results and Analysis

This section presents the results of the image segmentation and depth estimation processes, followed by an integrated analysis of their combined output. A comprehensive evaluation and interpretation of these findings are also provided, offering insights into their implications and significance within the context of the research.

3.2.1 Results of Object Detection and Image Segmentation

In the Table 3.1, the Mask R-CNN models utilize various backbones for feature extraction, such as ResNet-50 (R50) and ResNet-101 (R101), with options like C4 for convolutional stages, DC5 for dilated convolutions, and FPN for multi-scale feature detection. ResNeXt-101 (X101) incorporates grouped convolutions to balance accuracy and efficiency. YOLO models (v8 and v9) differ in size and computational requirements, with YOLOv8 ranging from nano (n) to extra-large (x), with segmentation capabilities indicated by “seg.” The YOLOv9 models (c and e) feature further architectural enhancements for improved accuracy. The $mAP_{box50-95}$ and $mAP_{mask50-95}$ metrics represent the mean Average Precision (mAP) for evaluating object detection (bounding boxes) and instance segmentation (masks), respectively, across multiple Intersection over Union (IoU) thresholds ranging from 0.50 to 0.95 in increments of 0.05.

We trained for 100 epochs on our small branches dataset, yielding the results shown in Table 3.1. These results reveal that YOLO models significantly outperform Mask R-CNN in both box and mask mAP, with YOLOv8 and YOLOv9 achieving over 77% $mAP_{mask50-95}$, whereas Mask R-CNN struggles to reach 12%. This highlights YOLO’s superior performance in real-time detection and segmentation tasks on the branches dataset, likely due to its end-to-end design, while the two-stage approach of Mask R-CNN performs less effectively for this task.

Table 3.1: Performance Comparison of Mask R-CNN and YOLO Models on our Branches Dataset(Only trained for 100 Epochs)

model	Branches	
	mAP _{box50-95}	mAP _{mask50-95}
Mask R-CNN R50-C4	76.86	0.06
Mask R-CNN R50-DC5	77.54	9.16
Mask R-CNN R50-FPN	79.19	6.75
Mask R-CNN R101-C4	88.05	0.05
Mask R-CNN R101-DC5	79.12	9.94
Mask R-CNN R101-FPN	84.09	2.95
Mask R-CNN X101-FPN	85.52	11.55
YOLOv8n-seg	98.9	77.4
YOLOv8s-seg	99.5	82.0
YOLOv8m-seg	99.6	81.6
YOLOv8l-seg	99.2	80.1
YOLOv8x-seg	98.7	77.1
YOLOv9c-seg	98.9	80.9
YOLOv9e-seg	98.8	80.0

Figure 3.3: Prediction Results Using the YOLOv8n-seg Model Trained for 100 Epochs on the Branches Dataset

3.2.2 Depth Map Results Obtained Through SGBM and WLS Post-Processing

The original left and right images were captured by the ZED Mini stereo camera. These images are preprocessed using smoothing techniques to enhance quality and reduce noise. We then apply the SGBM, followed by WLS filtering, to produce the final disparity map. The depth map is subsequently generated using equation (10). The results demonstrate in Fig.3.4 that most points on the tree branches are accurately represented with clear depth information. However, some regions exhibit mismatches on the branches, indicating areas of incorrect correspondence or depth estimation.

(1) Monocular depth estimation: The branches are positioned at distances of 1m, 1.5m, and 2m from the camera for testing using a monocular camera. The results are illustrated in Fig. 3.5. At a distance of approximately 2m, the image quality noticeably deteriorates, resulting in significant blurring that makes it challenging to discern the depth information around the branches.

(2) Stereo depth estimation: Using the simplest structure of PSMNet, a stereo depth neural network, we evaluated several pretrained models and performed additional fine-

Figure 3.4: Show the original images, pre-processed images, and disparity maps. (a) and (b) are the original left and right images. After pre-processing, we get (c) and (d). Then we use SGBM to create the disparity map (e), and apply WLS to get the final result (f).

Figure 3.5: Comparison of Predicted Depth Maps of Tree Branches Generated by MiDaS and Depth Anything Models at Branch Distances of 1m, 1.5m, and 2m from the Camera

tuning for 100 epochs on the SceneFlow, KITTI2012, and KITTI2015 datasets. As shown in Fig. 3.6, the results indicate that further fine-tuning on the original datasets did not improve performance when applied to our branch dataset. Therefore, it is unnecessary to perform additional fine-tuning on the original datasets before adapting the model to our specific branch dataset.

Figure 3.6: Comparison of PSMNet Fine-Tuning Results Across Different Datasets and Additional Fine-Tuning Epochs

We subsequently performed fine-tuning pre-trained model using the KITTI2015 dataset, adapting it to our branch dataset with various stereo neural network models to predict depth maps. The results, shown in Fig. 3.7, indicate that among the models (a) to (e), RAFTNet neural network provided the clearest depth information around the branches. Therefore, we utilized RAFTNet as the backbone within NeRF for fine-tuning, resulting in the output depicted in (f). We observed that the NeRF method provided the highest clarity around the branches, but it came with the trade-off of the longest processing time, taking approximately 6 seconds.

3.2.3 Final Results Achieved by Combining YOLO with NeRF Method

We employed YOLOv8n-seg as the instance segmentation model. Utilizing the original combination method[51], a comparative analysis was conducted between two leading depth estimation models, SGBM and NeRF, as demonstrated in Fig. 3.8. The resulting data distribution is presented in Fig. 3.9. The analysis indicates that while SGBM primarily detects points within a more accurate depth range, it yields fewer detected points compared to NeRF. Consequently, future research will focus on enhancing depth map accuracy for tree branches through the application of NeRF, with the aim of approximating ground-truth depth data. Nonetheless, a key limitation of NeRF is its processing time, currently requiring approximately 6 seconds to generate a depth map. Addressing this computational efficiency will be a major priority in our subsequent investigations.

Figure 3.7: Comparison of Depth Map Results from Different Stereo Matching Models

Figure 3.8: YOLO Combined with SGBM and NeRF Across Varying Distances: (a)-(c) Representing SGBM at 1 meter, 1.5 meters, and 2 meters; (d)-(f) Representing NeRF at 1 meter, 1.5 meters, and 2 meters

Figure 3.9: YOLO Combined with SGBM and NeRF Across Varying Distances Distribution: (a)-(c) Represent SGBM at 1 meter, 1.5 meters, and 2 meters; (d)-(f) Represent NeRF at 1 meter, 1.5 meters, and 2 meters

In Fig. 3.10, we present the triangular integration method developed in this research. This method optimizes memory usage by capturing only a select number of key points, rather than mapping all points within the plane, to accurately record the positions of tree branches. Such an approach is expected to be highly beneficial in future applications, particularly in scenarios where drones are required to navigate and operate in complex environments with dense tree branch structures.

Figure 3.10: (a) Results of the second method, where the final centroid points are calculated from three predicted points spaced a certain distance apart, and (b) display the depth map obtained from NeRF. Combining these allows for determining the final distance between the branches and the stereo camera.

3.3 Summary

This preliminary research integrates branch detection and segmentation with high-precision depth maps using deep learning models to improve distance measurements for drone-assisted tree pruning. While NeRF-based depth map generation offers high accuracy, its slow processing speed is a challenge. To mitigate this, efficient models like YOLO for branch detection and SGBM for depth generation were selected for their performance and reliability. Future work will involve using drones to gather a more diverse dataset to further enhance model robustness in complex environments.

Chapter 4

Proposed Contributions and Project Plan

4.1 Proposed Contributions

This research will make original and significant contributions to the detection of Radiata Pine tree branch locations for drone-assisted tree pruning. The key contributions are outlined as follows:

- (1) The research will establish a comprehensive dataset of Radiata Pine branches, collected using the Stereolabs ZED Mini binocular camera. This dataset will be uniquely valuable as it incorporates data from both indoor and outdoor scenarios, addressing the impact of environmental factors like sunlight on image quality. Additionally, the study will refine data pre-processing techniques, including filtering out blurred or overexposed images, and contribute labeled data for detection, segmentation, and depth map creation. The accurate depth maps generated as part of this work will be crucial for advancing research in drone-assisted tree pruning and related applications in forestry. Ultimately, this dataset will provide a valuable resource for future studies focused on applying AI and computer vision techniques to tree analysis and environmental monitoring.
- (2) This research will provide a method for detecting Radiata Pine branches and simultaneously measuring their distance from the camera, enabling precise pruning operations. The process is structured into three critical components: branch detection, depth map generation, and spatial distance measurement, offering a systematic approach for determining the exact spatial position of branches that require pruning. The detection of circular areas around branches and the creation of depth maps will introduce an innovative method for capturing three-dimensional spatial information in forestry environments. A key contribution of the research will be the integration of this method into a drone system for practical testing, advancing the application of AI-driven technologies in automated pruning and forestry management.
- (3) This research will provide a more efficient and interpretable depth map generation methods that can be deployed on cost-effective drones, making the technology viable for commercial use. By optimizing the Semi-Global Block Matching (SGBM) algorithm using the Enlightenment Algorithm, the study is expected to reduce the computational load while maintaining high accuracy, allowing the algorithm to run on drones with limited GPU resources. This advancement will make it feasible to apply advanced

depth map generation techniques on affordable drones, paving the way for commercial applications in industries such as precision agriculture, forestry management, and automated tree pruning. The integration of this optimized approach into low-cost drone systems is expected to significantly lower the barriers to adopting AI-driven solutions in these sectors, making the technology accessible and scalable for broader commercial deployment.

- (4) This research will contribute to advancing both image segmentation and depth estimation techniques by developing a robust and accurate model for detecting Radiata Pine branches. The study will refine the image segmentation algorithm, improving its accuracy and reliability in identifying tree branches. By integrating the improved depth estimation model with the segmentation model, the research is expected to enhance the overall performance of branch detection. Additionally, the study will optimize the computational performance of these models, reducing processing time and resource usage while maintaining high accuracy. This optimization will enable real-time deployment of the models on drones, allowing for precise and efficient branch detection and positioning for pruning operations. The advancements made in this research is expected to facilitate more efficient drone operations in forestry management and contribute to the commercialization of AI-driven pruning technologies.

4.2 Overview of Project Plan

This research’s plan consists of five phases, as outlined in Table 4.1. The initial phase has already been completed, and some progress has been made in the early stages of the second phase during the provisional registration period. Phases 2 to 4 encompass the primary research objectives outlined in this proposal. The final phase involves the writing and submission of the research. Table 4.2 provides an estimated timeline for the upcoming phases of the research, serving as a guiding reference for the ongoing work.

Table 4.1: Phases of research plan.

Phase	Description	Duration (Months)
1	Reviewing literature, overall design and writing the proposal	12 (complete)
2	Using the ZED Mini camera mounted on a drone to gather data on radiata pine trees	4 (partly)
3	Performing instance segmentation and depth information labeling on the collected data	3
4	Developing multiple instance segmentation models	4
5	Optimizing SGBM parameters to enhance depth map generation.	2
6	Developing multiple depth estimation models	2
7	Developing multi-task neural network architectures	3
8	Applying developed models to the drone for testing	2
9	Writing the research	4

4.3 Research Timeline

An estimated timeline for the remaining phases of the work to be conducted in the next thirty months is presented in Table 4.2. The first column stands for the research phase from

Table 4.2, the second column shows the detailed tasks and the subsequent columns stand for month periods.

Table 4.2: Research timeline for the next 24 months.

Phase	Task	Duration (Months)											
		2	4	6	8	10	12	14	16	18	20	22	24
n/a	Update the literature review	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
2	Capture RGB images of branches from left and right cameras, along with their intrinsic and extrinsic parameters.	✓											
2	Label bounding boxes and instance segmentation on the collected RGB images.		✓										
3	Develop NeRF and 3D Gaussian Splatting to generate depth maps for precise comparison with ground truth.			✓	✓								
4	Develop YOLO, Mask R-CNN, U-Net, and other methods to train the instance segmentation model.				✓	✓							
5	Use heuristic algorithms to optimize SGBM parameters for high-quality depth maps at high frame rates.						✓	✓					
5	Develop neural network models such as PSMNet, GwcNet, ACVNet, and MobileStereoNet to train the depth estimation model.						✓	✓					
6	Developing multi-task neural network architectures								✓				
7	Applying developed models to the drone for testing									✓			
8	Writing the draft of the research											✓	
8	Revise the final draft and prepare for presentation												✓

4.4 Research Outline

The outline of this research will be organized as follows.

- *Chapter 1: Introduction*
This chapter will introduce the problem statement, motivations, research objectives, contributions and research outline.

- *Chapter 2: Literature Review*
This chapter will first provide an in-depth discussion of various instance segmentation and depth estimation methods, including standard approaches and neural network architecture search optimization. Subsequently, a comprehensive review of existing methodologies for addressing instance segmentation and depth estimation challenges will be conducted. Finally, the ultimate objective of this research is to apply these techniques to drones for the purpose of automated branch pruning.
- *Chapter 3: Data collection instance segmentation and depth information labeling*
In this chapter, we will gather data on radiata pine trees and perform instance segmentation and depth information labeling on the collected data. We will explore different approaches for segmenting branches and extracting depth features, considering the sequence of steps involved in data collection and processing. Techniques to enhance segmentation accuracy will be introduced, along with strategies to improve depth estimation using stereo imagery. A method for optimizing data representation will also be developed to better capture the characteristics of tree branches. Finally, the effectiveness of these approaches will be compared and analyzed.
- *Chapter 4: Instance segmentation models*
In this chapter, we will focus on developing instance segmentation models for radiata pine trees. Specifically, we will address challenges related to varying conditions during data collection, such as changing lighting or occlusion by overlapping branches. Adaptive segmentation models will be developed to handle both typical and challenging conditions. Additionally, feature selection techniques will be applied to refine the model by removing less relevant features, improving segmentation accuracy and efficiency. The effectiveness of these models under different scenarios will be analyzed to ensure robustness in practical applications.
- *Chapter 5: Depth estimation models*
In this chapter, we will develop depth estimation models for radiata pine trees, focusing on selecting suitable approaches for estimating depth information under varying conditions. Several depth estimation algorithms will be implemented and their performance compared. The models will be evaluated based on their accuracy, robustness, and ability to handle different attributes of the collected data, such as varying tree branch densities and occlusions.
- *Chapter 6: Multi-Task Neural Network Architectures*
In this chapter, the instance segmentation and depth estimation models will be extended to a multi-task neural network architecture that jointly addresses both tasks. A multi-objective approach will be developed to optimize the model performance in terms of accuracy, efficiency, and computational cost. Additionally, interpretability-related metrics will be considered to improve the transparency of the network, leading to the development of an explainable multi-task architecture.
- *Chapter 7: Applying Developed Models to Drone Testing*
This chapter will present the results of applying the developed models to a drone for real-world testing, in collaboration with the University of Canterbury Computer Vision team. The proposed algorithms will be evaluated in practical scenarios, focusing on tree branch detection and depth estimation in field conditions. The chapter will assess the effectiveness of these algorithms when deployed on drones, highlighting their performance in achieving accurate instance segmentation and depth estimation for precise pruning tasks.

- *Chapter 8: Conclusions and Future Work*

This chapter will summarize the key findings and contributions of this research, highlighting the improvements made in instance segmentation, depth estimation, and multi-task modeling. The limitations of the current work will be discussed, along with reflections on potential challenges. Finally, recommendations for future research directions will be provided.

4.5 Resources Required

4.5.1 Computing Resources

This research will need to run large computational experiments, which consume much memory space, processing power, and GPU resources. The School's grid computing facilities and GPU servers can meet the requirement. Other IT resources are also available in the School's system.

4.5.2 Library Resources

Access to the respective publications in this area is expected. Most of the required literature is already subscribed by the university library and is also available online.

4.5.3 Conference Travel Grant

Publications to the respective conferences in the research area are expected. Therefore, a travel grant from the university is needed to support essential conference travels.

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